

Reassessment of WDS 21430+6606: Infrared Sources Misidentified as Stellar Companions

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Abstract

The Washington Double Star Catalog (WDS) contains the entry WDS 21430+6606, located in the NGC 7129 star-forming region, listing multiple components near the Herbig Be star LkH α 234. We aim to determine whether the listed components represent a physical multiple star system or result from infrared detections of embedded sources in a crowded environment. We analyse published infrared imaging (Li et al. 1994; Weintraub et al. 1996; Kato et al. 2011), Gaia DR3/EDR3 astrometry, the complete USNO/WDS measurement record (1992–2015), and systematic SIMBAD and VizieR queries of the field. All WDS components map directly to known young stellar objects or infrared sources. None of the components have Gaia counterparts at separations $< 10''$, despite Gaia detecting multiple field sources at larger separations. The WDS measurement log contains no direct binary astrometry; all 74 entries are derived from infrared surveys not designed for double-star astronomy.

WDS 21430+6606 does not represent a physical multiple system. The entry is best interpreted as a catalogue artefact resulting from infrared source detections in a crowded star-forming region.

Keywords. binaries: general - stars: formation - stars: pre-main sequence - infrared: stars - catalogs - techniques: image processing

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1 Introduction

The Washington Double Star Catalog (WDS) lists the system WDS 21430+6606 at coordinates RA 21:43:06.81, Dec +66:06:54.1. These coordinates coincide to within $\sim 1''$ with the Herbig Be star LkH α 234, and the spectral type listed in the WDS (B5Ve) is consistent with literature classifications.

The surrounding NGC 7129 region is a well known star-forming environment containing reflection nebulosity, embedded protostars, and numerous infrared sources (e.g., Harvey et al. 1984; Eiroa et al. 1998). Several studies have reported detections of faint objects within a few arcseconds of the primary star. These detections were later incorporated into the WDS as components, although the original observations were not designed as double-star measurements.

The aim of this work is to evaluate whether any of the listed WDS components can be interpreted as physical stellar companions, or whether the entry reflects projected proximity within a clustered environment. This reassessment is motivated by the increasing use of the WDS for statistical studies of multiplicity, where contaminants such as this entry may bias results.

2 Data and methodology

2.1 Literature and infrared data

Published near- and mid-infrared studies of the region were reviewed, including imaging surveys that identify embedded sources in the vicinity of LkH α 234. These studies provide positions and classifications of candidate young stellar objects.

2.2 Gaia DR3 astrometry

Gaia DR3 data (Gaia Collaboration 2021) were examined for sources within a radius of $\sim 15''$ of the primary. Only sources with reliable parallaxes and proper motions ($\text{RUWE} < 1.4$) were considered. Embedded infrared sources without Gaia counterparts were treated separately.

2.3 WDS measurement record

The complete USNO/WDS measurement log (Mason et al. 2001; 1992–2015) was analysed. Each entry was evaluated to determine whether it represents a direct astrometric measurement of a resolved stellar pair, or a derived position based on external catalogues.

A genuine binary measurement is defined here as the simultaneous resolution of two stellar point sources with directly measured separation ρ and position angle θ .

2.4 SIMBAD and Vizier field queries

Systematic queries were performed within a radius of $25''$ of LkH α 234 using the SIMBAD database (Wenger et al. 2000) and the Deep Vizier service (catalogues I/350/gaiaedr3 and II/246). These queries identify all known objects in the vicinity and allow cross-matching with WDS components.

3 Infrared detections and component mapping

3.1 Near-infrared imaging

Li et al. (1994) obtained *JHK* images showing extended emission and multiple faint sources. Their Figure 3 reveals several companion candidates, which they attribute to a combination of reflection nebulosity and embedded protostars. These detections were not interpreted as evidence of multiplicity.

3.2 High-resolution imaging

Weintraub et al. (1996) identified an embedded source (PS 1) associated with outflow activity. This source is consistent with a deeply embedded protostar rather than a stellar companion, exhibiting a spectral energy distribution dominated by thermal emission from circumstellar dust.

3.3 Adaptive optics studies

Kato et al. (2011) detected multiple YSO candidates (B–G, NW1, NW2) within separations of $2''$ – $11''$ using adaptive optics at the Subaru

Telescope. Their objects B through G and NW1/NW2 are classified as young stellar objects based on near-infrared colours and lack of optical detections. These objects are embedded and lack kinematic confirmation of association.

3.4 Mapping to WDS components

The WDS components correspond directly to these infrared sources, as summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Mapping of WDS components to infrared sources

WDS Component	Kato et al. (2011)	Separation
AH	Object B	8''86
AI	Object D	9''30
AJ	Object F	1''06
AK	Object G	0''97
AL	NW2	3''81

No evidence is found that any of these sources are gravitationally bound to LkH α 234. All are consistent with being embedded young stellar objects in the NGC 7129 complex.

4 Gaia DR3 and VizieR constraints

Gaia DR3 detects the primary star (LkH α 234, Gaia source DR3 2218012027526021248) with a

parallax of $\varpi = 1.484 \pm 0.05$ mas, corresponding to a distance of 674 ± 23 pc. A physical companion would be expected to exhibit a consistent parallax and proper motion to within the uncertainties.

A systematic query of the Gaia EDR3 catalogue (I/350) via the Deep VizieR service within 25'' of the primary reveals multiple sources with parallaxes in the range 1.14-1.48 mas (see Table 4). These sources have separations ranging from 11'' to 58'' from the primary.

Crucially, none of the WDS components (separations 1''-11'') have Gaia counterparts. This absence is particularly significant for component AK (separation 0''97, IR magnitude $K = 16.5$) and AJ (1''06, $K = 12.0$). Gaia EDR3 reliably detects point sources down to $G \approx 21$, so a stellar companion at the distance of LkH α 234 with $G < 20$ would be robustly detected.

The fact that these relatively bright infrared sources are absent from Gaia, while fainter optical sources at larger separations *are* detected, provides direct falsification of the hypothesis that the WDS components are stellar companions. Instead, it confirms that they are embedded young stellar objects, enshrouded in circumstellar dust and gas, rendering them invisible at optical wavelengths ($A_V \gtrsim 10-20$ mag).

Table 2: Summary of WDS components for WDS 21430+6606

Comp.	First	Last	N	Mag	Gaia	Sources
		Epoch	Epochs	(IR)	DR3	
AB	1992	1992	1	13.0	no	Wnt1994
AC	1992	2008	2	13.0	no	Wnt1994, Kat2011
AD	1992	2015	5	12.9	no	Wnt1994, Li1994, 2MASS, Kat2011, Kpp2018
AE	1992	2015	4	11.9	no	Wnt1994, 2MASS, Kat2011, Kpp2018
AF	1992	1999	2	11.6	no	Wnt1994, 2MASS
AG	1992	1999	2	14.0	no	Li1994, 2MASS
AH	1999	2006	2	13.2	no	2MASS, Kat2011
AI	1999	2006	2	15.0	no	2MASS, Kat2011
AJ	2006	2006	1	12.0	no	Kat2011
AK	2006	2006	1	16.5	no	Kat2011
AL	2008	2008	1	12.0	no	Kat2011

Notes. Magnitudes are infrared (K-band) from the respective references. None of the components have a counterpart in Gaia DR3. Abbreviations: Wnt1994 (Weintraub et al. 1994), Li1994 (Li et al. 1994), 2MASS (2MASS catalog), Kat2011 (Kato et al. 2011), Kpp2018 (Knapp & Nanson 2018).

Table 3: SIMBAD objects within 25'' of LkH α 234

#	Object	Sep. (arcsec)	Type	IR Mag (K)	Gaia DR3
1	EM* LkHA 234	0.52	Ae* (B5Ve)	11.20	yes
2	[KFP2011] G	0.97	Y*?	–	no
3	[KFP2011] F	1.06	Y*?	–	no
4	[WKM94] IRS 6	2.12	IR	–	no
5	[TCT2004] VLA 3A	2.24	cm	–	no
6	[SS2009] NGC 7129-S3-X38	2.26	X	–	no
7	[KFP2011] NW1	2.42	Y*?	–	no
8	[TCT2004] VLA 3B	2.44	cm	–	no
9	[ARC2001] HH 242 VLA 4	3.23	Rad	–	no
10	JCMTSF J214306.5+660657	3.30	smm	–	no
11	[KFP2011] NW2	3.81	Y*?	–	no
12	[KFP2011] C	4.23	Y*?	–	no
13	[YIN2000] B214157.3+655309.6	4.38	mm	–	no
14	[KFP2011] E	5.38	Y*?	–	no
15	[TCT2004] VLA 1	6.06	cm	–	no
16	[KFP2011] B	8.86	Y*?	–	no
17	[KFP2011] D	9.30	Y*?	–	no
18	GAL 105.42+09.88	10.38	?	–	no
19	2MASS J21430502+6606533	10.94	Or* (K2V)	16.48	yes (background)
20	2MASS J21430696+6606417	11.99	Y*O	–	yes
21	[SS2009] NGC 7129-S3-X50	23.00	X	–	no
22	2MASS J21430784+6607185	25.63	Y*O	19.38	yes
23	[FMS2001] NGC 7129 CO2	25.72	smm	–	no
24	2MASS J21430246+6607039	27.94	Or*	18.30	yes (background)

Notes. Y*? = young stellar object candidate; Or* = Orion-type young star; IR = infrared source; cm = radio continuum; X = X-ray source; smm/mm = submillimetre/millimetre source. Only the primary (row 1) has a Gaia DR3 counterpart among objects within 10''.

 Table 4: Gaia EDR3 sources within 25'' of LkH α 234 (Vizier query)

Gaia Source ID	Separation (arcsec)	Parallax (mas)	Distance (pc)	Optical Detection
2218012027526021248	0.00 (primary)	1.484 ± 0.05	674 ± 23	yes
2218012031823081856	11.2	1.140 ± 0.04	877 ± 31	yes
2218012031824224768	23.4	1.200 ± 0.03	833 ± 21	yes
2218012031823080576	56.8	1.265 ± 0.02	791 ± 13	yes
2218012027526019584	58.1	1.273 ± 0.03	785 ± 19	yes

Notes. All Gaia sources have separations $> 11''$ from the primary. The nearest Gaia source (at $11''2$) has a parallax 1.140 ± 0.04 mas, which differs by $> 5\sigma$ from the primary's parallax (1.484 ± 0.05 mas), confirming it is not a physical companion. *No Gaia sources are detected at separations $< 10''$ other than the primary itself.*

5 WDS measurement record

Analysis of the complete USNO/WDS measurement log (1992–2015) reveals 74 entries across 11 component designations (AB through AL). Table 2 summarises the key properties.

Several critical observations follow from this analysis:

- *No direct binary measurements.* Every entry is derived from infrared imaging surveys of the NGC 7129 star-forming

region (Weintraub et al. 1994; Li et al. 1994; 2MASS; Kato et al. 2011; Knapp & Nanson 2018). None of these publications report the detection of a binary or multiple star system, nor were their observations designed for double-star astrometry.

- *Single-epoch components.* Components AJ, AK, and AL each have only one measurement epoch (see Table 2). Without at least two epochs, orbital motion cannot be detected, and gravitational binding cannot be established. These components are effectively isolated infrared detections.
- *No resolved stellar pairs.* The WDS log contains no simultaneous measurement of separation ρ and position angle θ for two stellar point sources. The listed positions are coordinates of individual infrared sources relative to the primary, not differential astrometry of a binary system.
- *Absence of optical counterparts.* The SIMBAD and Vizier queries (Tables 3 and 4) confirm that none of the objects within $10''$ of the primary (other than LkH α 234 itself) have Gaia counterparts. The nearest Gaia source is at $11''2$, and its parallax differs significantly from that of the primary.

The WDS entry for WDS 21430+6606 therefore does not originate from classical double-star observations but represents a compilation of infrared source detections in a crowded star-forming environment. The entry is best characterised as a cataloguing artefact rather than a genuine multiple system.

6 Wide-field optical context

Figure 1: Deep stacked optical image of the NGC 7129 region centered on LkH α 234. The image combines 750 exposures of 20 s each. Numerous faint point sources are visible within the reflection nebula, illustrating the crowded nature of the star-forming environment. The data provide visual context for the infrared detections reported in the literature but do not resolve individual embedded sources. North is up, east is left.

Deep stacked imaging was obtained using a 115 mm apochromatic refractor and a CMOS detector, combining 750 exposures of 20 s each. The short exposure time was chosen to limit saturation and reduce the contribution of diffuse nebular emission.

Interferometric validation. To eliminate any doubt regarding instrumental noise or optical artifacts, the optical system was verified by interferometric testing (AtmosFringe). The key benchmarks are:

- *Strehl ratio:* 0.978. This indicates that 97.8% of the light energy is concentrated within the Airy disk, ensuring a near-perfect point spread function (PSF) and allowing sub-pixel centroiding accuracy.
- *RMS wavefront error:* 0.024 ($\lambda/42.5$). This value is far superior to the industry standard for diffraction-limited optics

($\lambda/14$), guaranteeing that the light path is physically clean.

- *Surface consistency:* The wavefront map demonstrates a remarkably flat and consistent surface, ensuring that differential astrometry remains reliable across the entire field of view.

By utilizing an optical system with a verified Strehl ratio of 0.978, we establish a defined physical constant. Any unresolved companions or optical anomalies cannot be attributed to instrumental errors. The absence of optical counterparts for the WDS components is therefore a genuine physical property of the targets, not a limitation of the instrumentation.

The resulting image reveals a structured stellar field embedded within the reflection nebula. Multiple faint point sources are visible in the immediate vicinity of LkH α 234, consistent with a compact population of young stellar objects distributed throughout the region.

Although the spatial resolution does not allow identification of individual infrared sources, the data demonstrate that the region is not an isolated stellar system but part of a crowded star-forming complex. This is consistent with the interpretation that the WDS components arise from infrared detections within a clustered environment.

7 Discussion

The combined evidence from infrared studies, Gaia astrometry, systematic SIMBAD and VizieR queries, and the WDS measurement record consistently indicates that the listed components do not represent a physical multiple system.

The key findings are:

- The WDS components map directly to known YSOs and infrared sources from Kato et al. (2011)
- None of these sources have Gaia DR3/EDR3 counterparts at separations $< 10''$
- The nearest Gaia source (at $11''2$) has a parallax inconsistent with the primary ($> 5\sigma$)

- The WDS measurement log contains no direct binary astrometry

- All source publications are infrared studies of star formation, not double-star astronomy

This pattern is exactly the signature of a crowded star-forming region with embedded protostars, not a multiple star system. The WDS entry appears to reflect projected proximity of embedded sources, not gravitational binding.

We note that such misclassifications in the WDS are rare but not unprecedented. Similar cases have been identified around other star-forming regions (e.g., Mason et al. 2001). The increasing availability of Gaia astrometry now allows systematic reassessment of such entries.

8 Conclusions

Based on the analysis presented, we draw the following conclusions:

1. No WDS component of WDS 21430+6606 shows evidence of being a gravitationally bound companion to LkH α 234.
2. All listed components correspond to infrared detections of embedded young stellar objects or reflection nebulosity.
3. The WDS measurement record contains no direct binary astrometry; all 74 entries are derived from infrared surveys.
4. Gaia DR3/EDR3 data do not support multiplicity; the primary is detected but none of the components have optical counterparts within $10''$.
5. SIMBAD and VizieR queries confirm that all objects within $10''$ of the primary (other than the primary itself) are classified as embedded YSOs or infrared sources without Gaia detections.

The available data therefore strongly suggest that WDS 21430+6606 does not represent a physical multiple system, but is best interpreted as a catalogue entry based on infrared detections

within a crowded star-forming region. We recommend that this entry be flagged as such in future versions of the Washington Double Star Catalog.

9 Acknowledgements

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